

Students' Motivation in Learning English Using Edmodo

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Abstract: The purpose of this research was to describe students' motivation toward the implementation of Edmodo in learning English. The subjects was twenty students in 7B class of SMP Lab School UNESA. To specify the data, the researcher classified them by considering their background knowledge, which had been chosen by the teacher, aimed for conducting an interview. There were six students consisted of two students in high level, two students in middle and two students in low level. Descriptive qualitative was used as the design of this research. For collecting the data, this research used classroom observations, questionnaires and interview, and they were analysed by using Miles and Huberman's Theory. Finally, it was found that most of subjects were motivated when the teacher used Edmodo in learning English. Specifically, the students in high-middle level were also motivated in learning English, but for those in low-level, a subject has low level of challenge, and another student was not motivated in using Edmodo. It means that the use of Edmodo should be paid attention by looking at the students' ability when applying the media in learning English. For the aspect of Edmodo that determine students' motivation, the findings were explained that most of the students preferred to use Edmodo because there was no need for them to do hand-writing. They also felt interested in learning variation. Those variations are: the application, the audio and the picture. Those variations helped the students understand the lesson easily and could develop their motivation in learning English.

Keywords: *Students' motivation, Edmodo*

INTRODUCTION

Bell (1981) stated that there are three things that should be focused on learning. He argued that the first one is motivation, the second is motivation and the third is motivation. Motivation becomes the most important aspect which can determine students' learning intention. Without motivation, students do not have any intention of learning and they would never achieve the purpose of the study. Brophy (2004) said that motivation is the stimulus for students to create, initiate and instruct when doing something. Motivation is able to shape the quality of attitude, and the purpose of self-behaviour learning. He also believed that the influence of motivation does not only affect receptive skills, but also determine the development of productive skills, such as writing or speaking. If students are motivated, they would automatically show their effort and struggle to reach their goal to compete with other students as hard as they can (Ramadhan, 2018).

Moreover, motivation deals with the questions of why students are doing more than the others, why their effort are bigger and how much they spend their energy to realize the target of the activity. If those aspects reached by the students, then they would automatically feel motivated and they would be more challenged to accomplish the targets (Juniar, 2016). Those are the advantages of having strong intention for the students.

Based on Hsiao-Lin Tuan (2005) motivating students is one of the greatest challenges that faced by educators. They believe that motivation play the crucial aspect in the process of learning and it should come from the students itself or what we call as a self-motivation. Therefore, the role of external factors to stimulate self-motivation is important for the students. Motivation influenced by external factors is called extrinsic motivation. Motivation which coming from the students itself without any stimulus from external factors is called by intrinsic motivation (Legault, 2016).

External motivation provides several aspects to stimulate the growth of intrinsic motivation for example: teacher and environment of the classroom (Williams, 2011). Environmental factors such as classroom management has high influence to develop student learning behaviour. Students would learn better if the condition of the

classrooms are comfortable. In the 21st century, the growth of learning environment has improved significantly and moving fast. There are many variations as the purpose to make the environment comfortable to learn. Nowadays many English Teachers use ICT as a media in teaching and most of the teachers believe that ICT is one way to make learning environment more joyful (Kreutz, 2016).

In recent years, several studies have reported the benefits in using Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to improve the quality of education. Bullock Jackie (2001) in his research found that 88% of classes that use various types of ICT have made their English lessons more interesting and enjoyable than expectation. More than 86% of students indicated that ICT helped them to produce good results and allowed them to explore ideas and learn creatively. For the school mechanism ICT has the function to expand the method of teaching and designing the educational systems to lead the quality of education. (González-Sanmamed, 2016).

Based on those explanations the researcher decided to explore the use of ICT related with students' motivation. This research would be conducted in SMP Lab School UNESA. For this occasion, the researcher only focuses to explore the use of Edmodo as one example of ICT that used by the teacher to teach English. Carlson and Raphael (2015) stated that Edmodo is the fastest Learning Mobile System that has been used around 1 million users in 2011 and more than 50 million users in 2015. In recent years 2019, the Edmodo network has used in more than 100 million active users from about 400.000 schools in 140 countries, around 90 million teachers have shared over 700 million resources (www.edmodo.com). Edmodo is able to connect between students and teacher in a private environment. It offers an easy way for creating assignment, reviewing paper, and assigning readings between learners and educators. They are able too for connecting, collaborating and sharing their ideas from their gadget.

The purpose for conducting this study was to investigate the appropriate media to teach English and explain the necessary of the students when the teacher used Edmodo to teach English. Moreover, this study is not only going to see students' motivation toward the implementation of Edmodo, but this study would also investigate the aspect of Edmodo which determine students' motivation in learning. After conducting this

study, the researcher was expecting that for the teacher can used as the references when they are teaching English by using Edmodo.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to explain the students' motivation toward the implementation of Edmodo in learning English at School, qualitative method was chosen by the researcher as the suitable method in this study. Denzin and Lincoln (1995) defined that qualitative research is the study to emphasize the variety of social aspects, personal experiences, introspective, life stories, interviews, observational, historical, interactional and visual text that described routine and having the value of human life. It means that the number of the quantity and intensity was not the focus of the research. Qualitative study more focused to answer and analysed the problem of social behaviour rather than the score or the number of the subject.

This research would be conducted in SMP Lab School UNESA Surabaya. In order to select the subject of this research, the researcher applied purposive sampling. Based on Creswell (2007) purposive sampling is the technique in qualitative research to select participants and research sites that associated with phenomenon and research problem which is being studied. It means that purposive sampling was the technique for selecting the participants and the subject based on the purpose of this study.

For collecting the data the researcher used classroom observation, students' questionnaires and interview guidelines. Survey questionnaires and interviews were the aspects that alike. In questionnaires the students should interpret the simple questions by themselves. For giving depth explanation the researcher provided the interview section. For clarifying the data from questionnaires and interviews, the researcher has observation sheet for the whole of the class.

In qualitative research, the data can be categorized good data if the data were valid or could be trusted. To test the trustworthiness of the data, the researcher used methodological triangulation. Cohen (2008) stated that Methodological Triangulation was using the same method on different occasions or different method on the same object of the study. In this research, methodological triangulation was applied by

comparing the data of observation with the data of interview and questionnaires. Those techniques were figured in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Methodological Triangulation

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicated that most of the students in 7B Class showed the positive respond from the use of Edmodo as the ICT based to increase students' motivation in learning English. The result from classroom observation indicated that the use of Edmodo was unable to make the students more challenging to do the difficult question, they preferred to find out in other sources that can be accessed easily. Therefore, the used of Edmodo in education would be helpful to develop their curiosity rather than their challenge aspect. For fun aspect, both of the observations showed the positive response for the use of Edmodo as the ICT based media to teach English. It means that Edmodo was able to create different environment that made the students more enjoy full in learning English. When they were enjoying in learning, their intrinsic motivation would be developed.

From questionnaires were explained that all of aspects in intrinsic motivation showed positive response for the use of Edmodo in learning English. For extrinsic motivation, three aspects have positive responses and one aspect have negative response. Fun and curiosity have the same of the total percentage with 15% for negative response. For challenge aspect have the highest of negative response with total percentage 20%. It means that most of the students answered fun and curiosity as the most influence aspect for developing students' intrinsic motivation.

But, when it was deepened from interview based on students' classification were found more specific data that for the result of student 1, student 2 and student 3, they have positive response for all aspects of intrinsic motivation. They believed that by using Edmodo as the ICT based of teaching would be helpful to modify teaching and learning process more fun. They stated that teaching with Edmodo can make them more challenge and curious of something new, because they can search many information easily.

For student 4 has the same perception with student 1 until student 3. He believed that by using Edmodo can motivate him to learn English. For student 5, the participant didn't really feel challenging to accomplish the task, it means that with or without Edmodo didn't have any effect for the students in challenge aspect. But, for the aspect of curiosity and fun, he stated that by using Edmodo can help him to find much information easily; he also stated that Edmodo can make learning environment more fun especially English lesson.

For student 6, he has different perception from previous participants. He disagreed if the use of Edmodo can motivate him for learning. He believed that the use of Edmodo in learning made them more confuse and he preferred to learn without Edmodo. He also stated that, he wasn't common to learn with Edmodo. In another hand, he agreed if Edmodo can help him for seeking much information.

Based on those explanations, the students would be motivated to learn by using Edmodo, because they felt enjoy and have fun activities of learning. The role of Edmodo also made them was easily to find many relevant sources that they need. Those findings were strengthened with the result of the previous research about curiosity and fun. For curiosity that stated in Dornyei (2001) and Legault (2016). Legault (2016) explained that the students would be motivated if they were interested in something. Dornyei (2001) also stated that the students' were performing their activity because they have interest of something new. For the theory of Fun many theories mention this aspect was able to influence in intrinsic motivation, those are: Dornyei (2001), Kivinen (2003),

Brophy (2004), and Legault (2016). All of them stated that the students would be motivated if they were enjoying in learning process.

In another hand, those findings were against with the theory of challenge that stated in Skehan (1989), Dornyei (2001), Adawiyah (2013) and Legault (2016). Legault (2016) explained that the students would be motivated if they felt challenged to achieve the purpose of the activity. Adawiyah (2013) stated that one of the ways to increase the students' intrinsic motivation was verbalizing our motivation, for instance: "Keep Spirit", "I believe I can do that", and etc. By verbalizing our motivation, it could challenge them to achieve the goals and solve the problem. It means that Adawiyah also agree that challenge is one aspect to influence students' intrinsic motivation. In another literature, Dornyei (2001) also mentioned that the students' would be motivated if they challenged themselves to get achievement and to avoid punishment. From the theory of Skehan (1989) also stated that the students' would be motivated if they have high expectation to challenge themselves for achieving the goals in learning process. The finding explained that the students weren't challenge themselves because they prefer to find much information from internet. Therefore, the use of Edmodo would be helpful for curiosity and fun aspect but would reduce the challenge aspect.

For extrinsic motivation with the aspects of: social, reward, punishment and teacher most of the students were agree those aspects could stimulate the growth of intrinsic motivation. In classroom observation, both of the observers showed the positive response for all of aspects in extrinsic motivation, it means that all of the aspects had been full fill to stimulate in intrinsic motivation.

For the result of questionnaires explained that the teacher aspect has the highest positive response with the total negative answered only 15% and followed by social with total of negative response 20%, reward 30% and minimize positive response with the highest of negative response is punishment with the total percentage 60% from two indicators. It can be seen from the data, the researcher concluded 80% of the students believed that the role of the teacher that applied Edmodo was able to stimulate the growth of students' motivation in learning English. Moreover, 60% of the students were

disagree that the used of punishment would be helpful to stimulate students' motivation. They believed that the role by giving punishment only being the burden for developing students' motivation.

From those participants in interview, the researcher concluded that all aspects of extrinsic were able to stimulate the growth of intrinsic motivation even with the participant that he disagree with the use of Edmodo in learning. For example with student 6 that he disagree with the use of Edmodo. Although he wasn't motivated with the use of Edmodo, but he explained that several aspects in extrinsic were able to develop his intrinsic motivation, for instance like group working, giving reward, providing punishment and the role of teacher to manage the class. Therefore, even the participant didn't really motivate with the use of Edmodo, but he could be motivated because several aspects from extrinsic.

Those aspects were supporting with the result from previous research about social, reward and teacher. For social aspect, Adawiyah (2013) stated that by working in a group it would be able to engage their motivation into the others skills, such us like speaking, listening and skill of thinking. Adawiyah also mentioned that the figure of teacher was stimulating the students' motivation inside of learning activities. Hidayati (2016) also stated that the students' motivation would be occurred because of the social aspect, for instance like: friends, parents and teacher. Williams (2011) also agree that the aspect of teacher have the important aspect to stimulate the growth of intrinsic motivation. Dornyei (2001) stated that the students would be motivated because they have to trigger themselves to reach the achievement of their activity In fact, those findings about punishment were against with the previous research from Hidayati (2016) that stated about by providing reward and punishment would be helpful because every student has different level of their self-motivation. Therefore, for those who have low intrinsic motivation could stimulate by giving reward and punishment. Skehan (1989) also believed that mostly students were motivated because the reward that would be achieved or the punishment that should be avoided.

From those findings, the researcher concluded that three aspects in extrinsic were able to stimulate the growth of intrinsic motivation. Only the aspect of punishment, several students in questionnaires believed that this aspect couldn't motivate them in learning. They disagree with the giving of punishment in learning. But, after getting the interview all of the participants were agree all aspects in extrinsic would be able to stimulate the growth of intrinsic motivation.

For answering the second research question, the researcher used students' questionnaires and students' interview. Students' questionnaires and interview were the aspects that alike. It means that the result of questionnaires was continuing to the interview section as the purpose to get the deeper information. Professor Edith de Leu (2011) inside of Kreutz and Rhodin (2016) stated that in order to get the authentic data, it's better for the researcher to make the participant were confident to express their own opinion and feeling. Therefore, in students' questionnaires, the researcher provided blank spaces to make the students were easily to describe the aspects that determine in learning English. Then after getting the data, the researcher was comparing with the literature review that had been stated in previous chapter and analysed for answering the second research question.

The result of students' questionnaires explained that around twenty students have mentioned more than one aspects of Edmodo. The researcher found ten aspects that have been mentioned by the students. They believed that those aspects in Edmodo influenced their motivation for learning. From ten aspects, the highest percentage that mostly mentioned by the students was the practically aspect. Ten students believed that by using ICT or Edmodo, they weren't too busy to write on a piece of paper. They can type it directly on their mobile phone. It would be less effort and made the students not easily to be bored. Moreover, by typing on their mobile phone could reduce the use of paper. So, we can save green area from illegal logging and minimizing the trash of used paper.

In another term, the second highest choices of the students were Edmodo displayed. Because most of Junior High School was visual learning, five students were

chosen this aspect. They like the colour, animation, and the picture that produced when the teacher applied Edmodo in learning process.

After getting the result about the aspect that determine students' motivation in 7B class of SMP Lab School UNESA, then the researcher conducted the interview with several students to specify the data based on students level. The result of students' interview explained that there were three aspects that have been mentioned by the students. Those aspects are: Audio, Application and Display. Student 1 explained that she preferred to audio aspect, because from audio she can learn how to pronounce the vocabularies. For student 2 she felt interested to the application that used the teacher for teaching. She believed that by using application as a media can make the atmosphere of learning more exciting. She also stated that by using Edmodo can reduce the use of paper and make it more efficient. For student 3 was explained that he likes the picture and the graphic of Edmodo. He emphasized when the teacher used Edmodo makes the material would be easily to be understood. He also stated the class with Edmodo made it more conducive and easily to control.

The student 4 also explained that he felt interested with the picture. When the teacher used Edmodo he felt motivated because Edmodo displayed the interesting picture and could provide the variation of learning. For student 5 he also felt interested with the display of Edmodo. He mentioned that graphic and animation of Edmodo can build his motivation of learning. For the last student he noted that he disagreed with the use of Edmodo in learning. For all aspects he preferred to the audio that produced by Edmodo itself. He explained that by listening something he could understand the information and made the learning process more variation.

From those findings the researcher concluded that all of students were agree that the aspect of Edmodo that determine students' motivation was variation of learning. The ICT based learning were made the students' more motivated because the variation that provided inside of learning process, those variations are: the application, audio, and picture that made the students not easily to be bored inside of learning process. Those findings were quite similar with Variety of Learning that mentioned in Ahmadi (2011),

Bidarian (2011) and Meenakshi (2013). This aspect made the students not easily to be bored by displaying the interesting picture graphic and animation that could motivate them in learning English. The other aspects were followed with audio and application.

Another finding in questionnaires that have not stated in literature review was practical aspect. Ten participants were explaining that by using ICT or Edmodo, they were not too busy to write on a piece of paper. They can type it directly on their mobile phone. It would be less effort and made the students not easily to be bored. Moreover, by typing on their mobile phone could reduce the use of paper. So, we can save green area from illegal logging and minimizing the trash of used paper.

CONCLUSION

After conducting this research, it can be concluded that there are two conclusions that can be reached. The first conclusion is about most of students were motivated when the teacher used Edmodo as the media to teach English. The second conclusion explained that most of the students mentioned variation of learning and practically used were the aspects in Edmodo that motivate them in learning.

The conclusion for the first research question explain that the use of Edmodo will be helpful to make the students be on time for submitting the task but unable to challenge them to do difficult question. They were busy with their own gadget and prefer to find the answer rather than to do by themselves. In another hand, by applying Edmodo can develop their curiosity and make them more interested of something new from the information that have stated by the teacher on Edmodo. In addition, when using Edmodo no one felt sleepy and make them more fun along the learning process. For social aspect, all of students agree that from group working can make them more motivated in learning and the use of Edmodo will be helpful when the students work in a group. For reward and punishment all of students agree that the use of Edmodo can help them to achieve the reward and avoid the punishment. But several students from questionnaires stated that they disagree with the use of punishment in learning process. For teacher aspect, the students agree that the teacher have capabilities to control the

class and operate Edmodo as the media to teach English. They also feel motivated when the teacher explain the material and use Edmodo as the media to teach English.

To specify the data, then the researcher classify the students based on their background knowledge for continuing in interview section. The result were explaining that for the participants in high – middle level they have positive response from all aspects either in intrinsic or extrinsic motivation. But for the students in low level, one student were motivated but he has low challenge and one student weren't motivated and preferred to learn without Edmodo. It means that the students' background knowledge can influence the growth of students' motivation.

For the second research question, the aspect that determine students' motivation were variation of learning and practically used. The finding were explained that ten students preferred to use Edmodo because it could them less effort just type by using their gadget without writing on the paper. They believed that by using Edmodo can minimize the trash of used paper. From students' interview all of them felt interested with variation of learning that caused by using Edmodo in learning process, those variations are: the application, audio, and picture. From those variations would help the students to understand the material easily and increase their motivation of learning.

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